

STUDENT PERFORMANCE MANAGEMENT SYSTEM

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Background

Royal International School (RIS) is a private school located in Kurunegala. The school has been in operation for 30 years. Its current population is 2700 students and 240 staff members. The school conducts classes from Kindergarten to A/Ls. For their internal operations, few semi-automated systems are used (such as for the administration and management purposes). However, the student performance information is recorded and reported in the traditional way using report cards. This does not permit timely access to student information for both parents and staff.

System Analysis

Problem Analysis

A report card issued term-wise is the sole document that records, reports and communicates a term's academic results which indicates the individual marks for each subject of that term, the total marks, the class average and the student's position in the class. This is hardly analytical or illustrative of a student's performance. Further except for the class average figure there is no other information depicting a comparative analysis nor overall student performance for a particular subject. The aforementioned lacking pieces of information can be the key to improve individual student performance as well as enhance the quality of the education provided by the school.

Moreover, performance reporting is being concentrated around academics only. As a result, students, parents and teachers focus only on term end marks. This can result in unhealthy scenarios like a student excelling in sports being branded as weak due to poor marks, or on the other hand

students cramming only to get better marks with no extra-curricular performance.

Apart from these two main problematic areas, the current system is obsolete given the potential to incorporate new ways to do it better. The current system being paper based consumes a lot of time and effort. Students can easily get the report cards misplaced. At the end of the day, it might not be even communicated nor taken use of properly. The current system is also incompetent in keeping track of a student's overall performance throughout the whole student life at the school. This project is intended to overcome these drawbacks and effectively report student performance.

Requirement Analysis

The Business Requirements are summed up as follows:

- Easy-to-understand performance report generated and communicated at the conclusion of each of the three terms of the year using a database.

The Functional Requirements are basically:

- Recording and presenting academic related information along with graphical illustrations,
- Class management, Subject management and Test management
- Enrolling and access management of users

The Non-Functional requirements are performance, reliability, maintainability, security, usability and training.

System Development

Based on our data (*Figure 1*), process and user interface design we have developed a functional database, the program and user-friendly interfaces. The languages HTML, PHP were used to build the system and it was built from scratch. CSS and Bootstrap were used to enhance the interfaces. Further Chart.js was used to generate the charts.

Technologies used:

- Adobe Dreamweaver CC 2019 used for the development of both program codes and user interfaces
- MS SQL 5.7.26 for database management system
- WAMP (Windows Apache MySQL PHP) Server environment

Figure 4. ER Diagram

Conclusion

The main aim of this system is to provide a solution to record and report a student's overall performance in respect to Academic, Extracurricular activities such as Sports and Arts and then, Club Memberships, Leadership, Soft skills, Attendance, Discipline and Health. Given the wide scope of project against the time permitted, as the first phase we have completed an effective academics module which fulfills the said requirements. Incorporating all the modules through future efforts can make this project a serious tool that can enhance the benefits of quality education both individually and at large.

References

Tutorialspoint (2020) *PHP Tutorial*. Available at: <https://www.tutorialspoint.com/php/> (Accessed: 12 March 2020).

W3Schools (2020) *Graph with Chart.js*. Available at: https://www.w3schools.com/ai/ai_chartjs.asp (Accessed: 24 March 2020).